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THE GRID MONITOR

Usage and installation manual

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Abstract

The LDAP-based ARC Grid Monitor is a Web client tool for the ARC Information System, allowing to browse all the published information about the system. It makes use of the hierarchical information organization and the PHP LDAP module to provide a real-time monitoring and primary debugging for ARC-based grids.

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1 Introduction

Information services play a very important role in any computational grid architecture, being a nerve system of the Grid. Resource discovery, scheduling, monitoring and many other tasks are impossible without a reliable and up-to-date information about system components.

ARC Information System [3] provides a robust and dynamic model for accessing not only quasi-static information about resources and services, but also about such rapidly changing parameters like queue and job status. Being based on OpenLDAP [4], it can be easily interfaced to any browsing or monitoring tool, giving thus a user-friendly overview of all the testbed resources.

The Grid Monitor makes use of the LDAP module of PHP [1] to provide a Web client tool to browse the ARC information infrastructure. It is available in many human languages in order to follow browser localization settings or user preferences. This document gives a summary of its capabilities and usage guidelines.

2 Grid Monitor Modules

The structure of the Grid Monitor to great extent follows that of the ARC Information System [3]. The basic objects are defined by the following schema's objectclasses:

- nordugrid-cluster: a cluster
- nordugrid-queue: a queue at the cluster, accessible by the authorised users
- nordugrid-job: a Grid job, associated with a queue
- nordugrid-authuser: a user, authorized to submit jobs to a given queue

The Grid Monitor also uses the Virtual Organisation (VO) organisationalPerson and Storage Element nordugrid-se objectclasses, and their attributes.

For each objectclass, either an essential subset of attributes, or the whole list of them, is presented in an easily accessible inter-linked manner. This is realized as a set of browser windows, each being associated with a corresponding module. There are nine major modules :

- 1) The overall Grid Monitor
- 2) Cluster description
- 3) Queue details
- 4) Job information
- 5) User information
- 6) Attributes overview
- 7) Customizable search
- 8) List of storage facilities
- 9) Lists of active users

Each module displays both dynamic and static information: for example, a queue name is static, while the amount of running jobs in this queue is dynamic. Most of the displayed objects are linked to appropriate modules, such that with a simple mouse click, a user can launch another module, expanding the information about the corresponding object or attribute. Each such module opens in an own window, and gives access to other modules in turn, providing thus a rather intuitive browsing.

In what follows, these modules are described in details, giving an overview of their functionality and usage hints.

2.1 The Grid Monitor

The basic module, providing access to the most required information, is the Grid Monitor, showing the overall status of the system. It serves as a starting point for browsing the system information. The purpose of this module is to give a quick overview of the current status of the Grid infrastructure by showing the list of the available clusters and the most essential information about them: an alias, number of working processors, number of occupied processors and number of queuing jobs. In the current implementation, the main Grid Monitor window contains also the link to the user base of the infrastructure. Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the running monitor. All the information shown is dynamic, including organizational names (countries in this case).

Figure 1: The Grid Monitor

In Figure 1, the numbered tags indicate clickable objects as explained below:

- 1) Cluster: a cluster alias, linked to the cluster description module (Section 2.2), which provides complete information about the current status of a cluster.
- 2) Load: a graphical and numeric representation of the cluster load, showing both Grid- and non-Grid (submitted locally) running processes. Colored bar shows percentage of Grid processes, while the grey bar shows total relative occupancy of a cluster. Numbers indicate the absolute amount of running processes, with first figure corresponding to the Grid, and second - to the non-Grid ones. It should be noted that number of processes does not necessarily correspond to the number of running jobs: a parallel job can occupy several processors. By clicking on a bar, a user accesses the list of all Grid jobs, running on a cluster (Section 2.4).
- 3) Queuing: number of queuing jobs, which includes both jobs queued in an LRMS and those being pre-processed by the Grid Manager [2]. Only jobs which can be potentially executed in a Grid queue are counted. The number is linked to the same module as the Load item, with the only difference that it displays the list of the Grid-queued jobs. Note that non-Grid jobs are counted in the total number of queued jobs, while they can not be listed by the Grid Monitor, as they are not providing any information in the ARC Information System.
- 4) Search: link to the custom search interface (Section 2.7) which allows users to compose non-standard monitor requests.
- 5) Storage resources: link to the list of available storage resources (Section 2.8).

2.2 Cluster Description

The cluster description module displays all the cluster attributes stored in the local information tree, as well as most relevant information about the queues, accessible by the Grid users. The window thus contains two lists, as shown in Figure 2:

- 1) **Attributes:** this is a dump of all the attributes of the `nordugrid-cluster` objectclass, dynamic and static ones. Such attributes as cluster alias, or domain name, are static; others are dynamic, with the values obtained by the information providers: e.g., total CPU number, amount of jobs, or available disk space. More details about these attributes can be found in the ARC Information System description [3]. Each attribute (apart of the time stamps) is linked to the Attributes Overview module (Section 2.6), such that clicking on an attribute name brings the list of the values of this particular attribute on all the Grid clusters. For instance, this is the most convenient way to browse available disk space or runtime environment values over the system.
- 2) **Queues:** the list of queues at a given cluster, accessible by the Grid users. While the detailed list of queue attributes and corresponding jobs can be obtained by clicking on a queue name (see Queue Details module description, Section 2.3), the most essential parameters are listed already in the Cluster Description module. They are: queue name, queue status, queue length (minimal and maximal), number of CPUs assigned to a queue (if available), and number of running and queued jobs. Since queues can be shared between Grid and local users, the total number of jobs is shown, with the number of Grid jobs in parentheses.

The Cluster Description module is linked from most other modules (except the List of Users one): clicking on a domain name of a cluster brings the Cluster Description window.

2.3 Queue Details

In the ARC Information System, the `nordugrid-queue` objectclass is described by a set of queue-specific attributes, and has two sub-trees: `nordugrid-job` and `nordugrid-authuser`. This structure reflects the fact that users are not implicitly authorized to submit jobs to any queue. However, the list of users allowed to a specific queue is a fairly static information, and thus is beyond the scope of the Grid Monitor[†].

The Queue Details module provides the list of the queue attributes and of all the jobs scheduled (running or waiting) to this queue. Figure 3 shows the queue description window, with clickable fields marked by numbered tags as follows:

- 1) **Attributes:** the dump of the queue attributes. Just like the cluster attributes (Section 2.2), they can be both static and dynamic. Every attribute is linked to the Attributes Overview module (Section 2.6), which allows to browse the values of each attribute over all the Grid system.
- 2) **Cluster name:** each queue is associated with the cluster, which name is shown at the top of the window. Clicking the cluster name brings up the Cluster Description window (Section 2.2).
- 3) **Job name:** from the Queue Details window, users can get access to detailed information about every job in the queue by clicking the job name. Each job name is linked to the Job Information module, described in Section 2.4.
- 4) **Owner:** The Grid authentication mechanism allows to associate every job with a corresponding user, even though an actual Unix account owner may be a generic "griduser". The Grid Monitor uses this feature to display explicitly each job owner. In the Queue Details window (as in all other modules), user's name is linked to the User Information module (Section 2.5), which displays all the resources available for a given user, as well as the list of user's jobs.

Queue Information module is accessible via links to queue names in the Cluster Information (Section 2.2), Job Information (Section 2.4), User Information (Section 2.5) and Attributes Overview (Section 2.6) modules.

[†]List of queues available for a given user can be obtained through the User Information module

Figure 2: Grid cluster details

2.4 Job Information

The Job Information module is activated on three different occasions:

- To display a list of all running Grid jobs on a cluster
- To display a list of all queued Grid jobs on a cluster
- To show the full information on a given job

Lists of running and queued jobs are accessible from the top Grid Monitor window (Section 2.1) by clicking the corresponding fields (marked 2 and 3 in Figure 1). As shown in Figure 4, such a list contains not only job names, but also their respective owners, status (as returned by the Grid Manager), execution time (in case of running jobs), and the submission queue.

Most of the fields in a job list window are linked to the corresponding monitor modules, giving access to more detailed information:

- 1) Job name: just like in the Queue Details window (Section 2.3), the job name is linked to the Job Information window, described below. However, while the Queue Details module lists the jobs in a given queue, the Job Information window gives an overview of all the Grid jobs on a cluster.

Queue: jeannedarc.hpc2n.umu.se - atlas-t1-repro 2

Attribute	Value
Distinguished name	nordugrid-queue-name=atlas-t1-repro,nordugrid-cluster-name=jeannedarc.hpc2n.umu.se,Mds-Vom
objectClass	Mds
Queue name	nordugrid-queue
Queue status	atlas-t1-repro
Scheduling policy	active
Homogeneous queue	Maui
CPU type	TRUE
Memory (MB)	Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU @ 2660 MHz
Architecture	15800
Operating system	x86_64
Benchmark	Ubuntu
Walltime, max. (minutes)	8.04
Walltime, default (minutes)	hardy
Total occupied CPUs	SPECINT2000 @ 1920
CPUs occupied by Grid jobs	HEPSPEC2006 @ 9.67
Local jobs, queued	7200
Grid jobs, queued	30
Grid jobs, awaiting submission	0
CPUs, total	0
Mds-validfrom	0
Mds-validto	0

Job name	Owner	Status	CPU (min)	Memory (KB)	CPUs
1 Atlasinstall-17.0.2-AtlasProduction-10	Andrej Filipcic	DELETED			1
2 Atlasinstall-16.6.7-AtlasProduction-12	Andrej Filipcic	DELETED			1
3 Atlasinstall-16.6.7-AtlasProduction-13	Andrej Filipcic	DELETED			1
4 Atlasinstall-17.0.2-AtlasPhysics-9.1	Andrej Filipcic	DELETED			1
5 Atlasinstall-17.0.3-AtlasOffline	Andrej Filipcic	DELETED			1
6 Atlasinstall-16.6.7-AtlasProduction-14	Andrej Filipcic	DELETED			1
7 Atlasinstall-17.0.3-AtlasProduction-1	Andrej Filipcic	DELETED			1
8 Atlasinstall-17.0.3-AtlasProduction-2	Andrej Filipcic	DELETED			1
9 ritsem-cvmfs	Andrej Filipcic	FINISHED at 2011-09-03 14:30:16			1
10! uname	Ake Sandgren	FAILED			1
11! uname	Ake Sandgren	FAILED			1
12! snv-38-35011	Klas Markstrom	FAILED			1
13! snv-38-35026	Klas Markstrom	FAILED			1
14! snv-38-35034	Klas Markstrom	FAILED			1
15! snv-38-35055	Klas Markstrom	FAILED			1
16! snv-38-35069	Klas Markstrom	FAILED			1

Figure 3: Grid queue details

- 2) Owner: this field is also identical to the one in the Queue Details window: user's name is linked to the User Information module (Section 2.5), which displays all the resources available for a given user and the list of user's jobs.
- 3) Queue: the name of the queue is linked to the Queue Details window (Section 2.3), which gives a snapshot of the queue status, including all the Grid jobs submitted to a particular queue – running or waiting.
- 4) Cluster name: clicking on the cluster name brings up the Cluster Description window (Section 2.2), which gives a general overview of a given cluster and the status of its queues (those available for the Grid users).

The job information window is invoked by clicking on a job name in any Grid Monitor window which lists jobs. It is handled by the same module which produces running/queued job list, and contains simple dump of all the available job attributes (see Figure 5). Just like in the Cluster Description and Queue Description windows, each attribute is clickable (as indicated by a tag numbered 1 in Figure 5), and is linked to the Attributes Overview module (Section 2.6). This is a convenient way to compare jobs that reside on the system.

Jobs at korundi.grid.helsinki.fi 4

Job name	Owner	Status	CPU (min)	Queue	CPUs
1 N/A	uscmspilot149	INLRMS: R	154	mgrid	1
2 N/A	uscmspilot148	INLRMS: R	153	mgrid	1
3 N/A	uscmspilot07	INLRMS: R	153	mgrid	1
4 N/A	uscmspilot47	INLRMS: R	151	mgrid	1
5 N/A	uscmspilot10	INLRMS: R	151	mgrid	1
6 N/A	uscmspilot08	INLRMS: R	149	mgrid	1
7 N/A	uscmspilot50	INLRMS: R	149	mgrid	1
8 N/A	uscmspilot09	INLRMS: R	149	mgrid	1
9 N/A	uscmspilot06	INLRMS: R	148	mgrid	1

Figure 4: Grid job list

Job ID: *gsiftp://jade-cms.hip.fi:2811/jobs/38201313529597165580199*

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Attribute	Value
Distinguished name	nordugrid-job-globalid=gsiftp://jade-cms.hip.fi:2811/jobs/38201313529597165580199.nordugrid-info-gro
objectClass	Mds
	nordugrid-job
ID	gsiftp://jade-cms.hip.fi:2811/jobs/38201313529597165580199
Owner	/O=Grid/O=NorduGrid/OU=nbi.dk/CN=Robot.Nagios - Petter Urkedal
Name 1	srm
Execution cluster	jade-cms.hip.fi
Execution queue	arc
Execution nodes	c26.local
Submission machine	109.105.124.154:37871;mon-ngi.ndgf.org
Submission time (GMT)	2011-08-16 21:19:57
Erase time (GMT)	2011-08-19 21:21:08
Proxy expiration time (GMT)	2011-08-17 08:25:35
Job completion time (GMT)	2011-08-16 21:21:08
Client version	nordugrid-arc-0.8.3
Standard output file	testjob.out
Standard error file	testjob.err
Requested CPUs	1
Requested CPU time	15
Requested wall clock time	15
Used CPU time	0
Used wall clock time	0
Exit code	0
Status	FINISHED
Mds-validfrom	2011-08-16 21:41:42
Mds-validto	2011-08-16 21:42:12

Figure 5: Grid job statistics

2.5 User Information

The User Information module of the Grid Monitor gives access to all the available information, related to a given user. This includes the list of available resources (queues, processors and disk space), and the list of user jobs, residing on the system at the time of query. To collect this information, the whole system has to be queried, therefore invocation of this module typically takes quite a bit of time (at least comparing to most other modules).

Figure 6 shows a typical User Information window, where the numbered fields are linked to other Grid Monitor modules:

- 1) Job name: this field is linked to the Job Information window (Section 2.4), providing access to the detailed information on a given job. Unlike of Job Information or Queue Information modules, which list local to a cluster jobs, the User Information module collects all the jobs submitted by a given user to the whole system.
- 2) Cluster: since the User Information window displays all the jobs associated with a given user, description of each respective cluster is available by clicking the cluster name. This brings up a cluster description window, described in Section 2.2.
- 3) Queue: this field is linked to the Queue Details module (Section 2.3), thus giving access to the information about the status of the relevant queue.
- 4) Cluster: the upper part of the User Information window lists the Grid resources, available for a user. Each cluster, to which a user is authorized to submit jobs, is indicated by its name. Cluster names are linked to the Cluster Description window (Section 2.2), giving detailed information on available resources.
- 5) Queue: since users authorization may be not only cluster-based, but also queue-based, the allowed queue information can be accessed by clicking a queue name. This brings up the Queue Details window, described in Section 2.3.

User Information can be invoked from any Grid Monitor window where a user name is displayed (e.g., an Active Users list, a Job Information or a Queue Details window).

2.6 Attributes Overview

As it was mentioned above, every ARC objectclass attribute, appearing in a Grid Monitor window, is linked to the Attributes Overview module, which queries all the relevant objects on the system and delivers a

Information for Robot: Urkedal

Cluster:queue	Free CPUs	Queued jobs	Free disk (MB)
Distinguished name: /O=Grid/O=NorduGrid/OU=nbii.dk/CN=Robot: Nagios - Petter Urkedal			
dev012.gla.scotgrid.ac.uk does not answer			
mon01.grid.lumii.lv:condor_all	38	0	135155
grid.tsl.uu.se does not answer			
ce.lhep.unibe.ch:all.q	0	8	6822897
pikolijtsi:gridlong	2:20160	328	5240059
pikolijtsi:atlas-t1-repro	2:20160	14	5240059
vm009.gla.scotgrid.ac.uk does not answer			
arc02.lcg.cscs.ch:atlas	0	0	81577595
arc02.lcg.cscs.ch:lcgaadmin	0	0	81578847
arc01.lcg.cscs.ch:atlas	0	0	81576719
arc01.lcg.cscs.ch:lcgaadmin	0	0	81577461
Not authorised at host nordugrid.unibe.ch			
jost.arnes.si:default	12	171	2038005
jeannedarc.hpc2n.umu.se:arc	0	0	628474
ce01.titan.uio.no:normal	570	0	7759462
arc-ce01.pdc.kth.se:sassy	0	0	2186266
arc-ce.smokerings.nsc.liu.se:arc	80	203	2550090
gateway01.dcs.ku.dk:tier1	0	2130	566753
siri.lunarc.lu.se:arc	0	4	3911887
Not authorised at host grid.uio.no			
grid03.unige.ch:production	0	0	1424626
grad.uppmax.uu.se:grad	0	1135	2273957
arc.bccs.uib.no:t1	0	0	990641
arctest-ce.smokerings.nsc.liu.se:arc	48	202	1048284
ce03.titan.uio.no:normal	592	0	7864320
testbed-arc0.grid.upjs.sk does not answer			
vuori-arc.csc.fi:grid-ops	1072	0	12465878
usva.fgi.csc.fi:grid	0	0	459501
Can use a total of 26 sites			

Job name	Status	CPU (min)	Cluster	Queue	CPUs
1 srm	FINISHED	N/A	mon01.grid.lumii.lv	condor_all	1
2 gridftp	FINISHED	N/A	mon01.grid.lumii.lv	condor_all	1
3 jobsubmit	FINISHED	N/A	mon01.grid.lumii.lv	condor_all	1
4 gridftp	FINISHED	N/A	mon01.grid.lumii.lv	condor_all	1
5 lfc	FINISHED	N/A	mon01.grid.lumii.lv	condor_all	1
6 lfc	FINISHED	N/A	mon01.grid.lumii.lv	condor_all	1
7 srm	FINISHED	N/A	mon01.grid.lumii.lv	condor_all	1
8 srm	FINISHED	N/A	mon01.grid.lumii.lv	condor_all	1
9 jobsubmit	FINISHED	N/A	mon01.grid.lumii.lv	condor_all	1
10 srm	DELETED	N/A	pikolijtsi	gridlong	1
11 jobsubmit	DELETED	N/A	pikolijtsi	gridlong	1
12 gridftp	DELETED	N/A	pikolijtsi	gridlong	1
13 lfc	DELETED	N/A	pikolijtsi	gridlong	1

Figure 6: Grid user information

comparative list of the attributes. Similarly to the User Information module, querying all the Grid resources takes somewhat long time, as the Grid Monitor does not have an own cache.

This module can also be accessed via the search interface (Section 2.7). In this case, it can list as many attributes as specified by a user request, eventually applying the user selection criteria.

Object	Jobs, total amount
1 Cluster ce.lhep.unibe.ch	461
2 Cluster pikolijtsi	1601
3 Cluster arc02.lcg.cscs.ch	6339
4 Cluster arc01.lcg.cscs.ch	6323
5 Cluster nordugrid.unibe.ch	339
6 Cluster jost.arnes.si	421
7 Cluster jeannedarc.hpc2n.umu.se	3592
8 Cluster ce01.titan.uio.no	3806
9 Cluster arc-ce01.pdc.kth.se	1295
10 Cluster arc-ce.smokerings.nsc.liu.se	835
11 Cluster gateway01.dcs.ku.dk	5997
12 Cluster siri.lunarc.lu.se	1461
13 Cluster grid03.unige.ch	518

Figure 7: Grid objects grouped by attribute

Figure 7 shows a typical result of the Attributes Overview query: in this example, the nordugrid-cluster attribute "Jobs, total amount" was queried, and a comparative list of results returned. The Resource field (indicated by the tag 1) depends on the nature of the attribute, and can be either of:

- cluster name, linked to the Cluster Description module,
- cluster name and queue name, linked to the Cluster Description and Queue Details modules respectively,
- job ID string (see ref.[2] for details), linked to the Job Information module.

2.7 Custom search

The custom search is a customizable interface to the Attributes Overview module (Section 2.6). It allows users to choose which attributes of an object to display, optionally applying filters. While the other Monitor windows display a pre-defined set of data, this module gives an advanced user a possibility to build a customized request to the Information System.

An example use case for this interface could be a user desiring to view a list of his running (but not queued or finished) jobs, complete with used CPU and wall time, memory and job name. The search tool would be then invoked for the job object, and the display request would contain Name, Used CPU time, Used wall time, Used memory (KB), and Status – the latter with a filter `Status = INLRMS: R`.

The screenshot shows a window titled "Display resources or objects of your choice". It contains a dropdown menu for "Resource / object" with "job" selected, a text input for "Nr. of attributes (def. 6):" with the value "4", and a "Next" button.

Figure 8: Object class selection window

Figure 8 shows the first screenshot of the search interface, which welcomes users to select the object class to work with, and the amount of attributes to be displayed. When not sure about the latter, users should specify a top estimate – unused fields will be ignored in further searches.

The screenshot shows a window titled "Define attributes to display for the object: cluster". It contains several rows of input fields for defining filters. The first row is "Cluster alias" with an empty field. The second row is "Operating system" with a tilde operator and "redhat". The third row is "CPUs, total" with a greater-than-or-equal operator and "100". The fourth row is "Postal code" with an exclamation mark operator and "SE". The fifth row is "-----Select one-----" with an empty field. There are "Reset", "SHOW", and "START OVER" buttons.

Figure 9: Attribute selection window

Figure 9 is a snapshot of the screen where the attributes to display and their selection criteria are specified. If a user wishes to display an attribute for all the objects, independently of its value, the rightmost field may be either kept empty, or filled with an asterisk (*), while the middle field should be set to “=”. Whenever a filter has to be applied, an operator should be selected in the middle column, and a match string specified in the rightmost field. For example, if only clusters containing “NBI” in their domain names have to be shown, the attribute filter would be `Front-end domain name ~ nbi`. Matches are case-insensitive.

The screenshot shows a table with the following data:

Object	Cluster alias	Operating system	CPUs, total	Postal code
1 Cluster <i>murska-arc.csc.fi</i>	Murska	Redhat	2176	FI-2101

Below the table are "BACK" and "START OVER" buttons.

Figure 10: Customized cluster information display

Figure 10 is the result of the search according to the criteria defined in the example in Figure 9. Three filters were applied: on operating system attribute, total number of CPUs and postal code (in this case we were

selecting any cluster which is not in Sweden). Since we wanted to display each cluster’s alias as well, this attribute was added to the selection, but with a “match everything” scope. The attribute matching method is exactly the same as used by the Attributes Overview module (Section 2.6), and it re-uses the screen layout shown in Figure 7.

2.8 Storage Resources

Although there is no well-defined Storage Element concept in ARC, some information about the storage resources can be found in the Information System. The Storage Resources module, linked from the main Monitor window, displays all the available information for those Storage Elements which publish it. Particularly important is the base URL, which specifies the Grid mount point that could be used in job descriptions.

Storage Elements

#	Alias	Free/total space, Gb	Name	Base URL	Type
1	KE-VLS-gacl	0/0	storage:vls.grid.upjs.sk	gsiftp://vls.grid.upjs.sk:2811	gridftp
2	KE-Alice-unixac>	88/332	unixacl:alice.grid.upjs.sk	gsiftp://alice.grid.upjs.sk:2811/unixacl	gridftp
3	KE-Alice-gacl	88/332	gacl:alice.grid.upjs.sk	gsiftp://alice.grid.upjs.sk:2811/gacl	gridftp
4	KE-Alice-SSE	88/332	smartse:alice.grid.upjs.sk	sse://alice.grid.upjs.sk/sse	SSE
5	TEST SE for AtI>	25/31	sename:nordug.bitp.kiev.ua	gsiftp://nordug.bitp.kiev.ua:2811/	gridftp
6		31707/57272	storage:uagrid.org.ua	gsiftp://uagrid.org.ua:2811/storage	gridftp
7	KNU Cluster SE,>	655/2064	pub:arc.univ.kiev.ua	gsiftp://arc.univ.kiev.ua:21/pub	gridftp
8	KNU Cluster SE,>	655/2064	sse:arc.univ.kiev.ua	sse://arc.univ.kiev.ua/sse	SSE
TOTAL		35386/69427			

Figure 11: List of storage elements

different

3 Implementation notes

The Grid Monitor is implemented entirely in PHP, with optional usage of client-side JavaScript. Since all the databases the Grid Monitor has to deal with are hierarchical LDAP ones, the server-side LDAP module of PHP is absolutely necessary to be enabled in order to make the Grid Monitor functioning. The PHP LDAP module conveniently allows parallel LDAP searches, – the feature heavily used by the Grid Monitor, since it speeds up the data retrieval.

The Grid Monitor uses only minimal disk caching (overview window only), storing all the LDAP query results in the memory. To minimize memory usage, only the attributes relevant to each query are retrieved.

The basic principle of information discovery in ARC is to traverse EGIIS indexing services harvesting ARIS end-points, and then poll each ARIS (normally, in parallel).

Since the ARC architecture makes use of several equivalent bootstrap top-level EGIIS servers, the Monitor queries all of them in order to have a reliable access to all the system information. In some cases, lower-level ARIS servers can also be duplicated, hence the Monitor contains a built-in mechanism to filter duplicates.

Discovery of lower-level ARIS servers is done recursively, starting from the registration information in all the top-level indexes, and ending at the local level. This recursive search method is invoked not only to discover clusters in e.g., the main Monitor module, but also to locate storage facilities.

All the Grid Monitor windows are automatically refreshed by the means of the built-in browser HTML instructions. Every window can be forcefully refreshed, printed and closed by using either standard browser tools, or the provided JavaScript-enabled buttons.

In the top Monitor window, clusters are automatically grouped by geographical location. Alternatively, users may chose to order them by e.g. capacity or load.

Such fields as cluster aliases, user names and attribute names, are customizable, and can be adjusted from the stored in the information system values to any more appropriate ones, depending on the actual requirements.

In general, the Grid Monitor was designed to be a cross-browser, cross-platform tool, and have been shown to work properly with all known browsers.

4 Installation and configuration

LDAP-based ARC Grid Monitor is distributed in the *nordugrid-arc-ldap-monitor* RPM and DEB binary packages available in a variety of repositories (Fedora, Ubuntu, NorduGrid, EMI, UMD), and can therefore be deployed in a standard manner by a system administrator.

However, being just a set of PHP scripts, Monitor can also be deployed by any non-privileged user by unpacking the contents of the packages, or obtaining the scripts from the ARC code repository. Please consult README file distributed with the package for necessary dependencies and configuration suggestions.

The Monitor can be installed via manual unpacking on any non-Linux operating system which has an HTTP server with PHP enabled, and PHP's LDAP and GD modules installed. Consult PHP installation notes on a given system for details.

Be generous when configuring PHP memory consumption limits: few dozen megabytes may be needed, depending on the size and load of your infrastructure.

In general, the following software must be present at the Web server that wishes to host the Monitor:

1. GD library (e.g. <http://www.boutell.com/gd/>)
2. OpenLDAP library (e.g. <http://www.openldap.org>)
3. PHP4 or PHP5 (<http://www.php.net>) with OpenLDAP and GD modules (available with all common distributions)
4. HTTP server with PHP4 or PHP5 (commonly available as well)

In order to install the Monitor manually, do the following:

1. unpack the files in a folder accessible by your HTTP server;
2. verify that this folder contains a directory called `cache` and that it is writable by the HTTP server. If your server is configured to have write access only to a specific location, such as e.g. `../htdata`, modify `CACHE_LOCATION` value in `includes/settings.inc` accordingly;
3. modify `includes/settings.inc` according to your information system structure and liking: most likely, you want to modify the bootstrap `$giislist` array by removing some servers and adding other(s). By default the Monitor is configured to poll NorduGrid servers;
4. test installation by opening file `loadmon.php` in a browser. More verbose output for debugging purposes can be achieved by using `loadmon.php?debug=1` or `loadmon.php?debug=2`.

Configuration of few necessary parameters is done via the file `includes/settings.inc`. Normally, no adjustments are needed, except of the bootstrap tuning explained above.

To make output more human-readable or adjust it for your mother tongue, you may wish to modify translations in `/lang/*.inc` and strings in `includes/cnvrname.inc` and `includes/cnvalias.inc`.

In order to avoid misbehaving sites from being polled, modify `includes/blacklist.inc`: filtering is switched on by flag "1". Otherwise, the file is not needed and can even be removed.

5 Acknowledgements

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